

ASSESSMENT OF SOIL EROSION AND SEDIMENT TRANSPORT IN RIVERBANKS USING REMOTE SENSING AND GIS TECHNIQUES

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Abstract

This research paper focuses on the application of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Remote Sensing (RS) technologies to analyze groundwater potential zones in the Bindusara Watershed, located in Beed District, Maharashtra. Groundwater, a critical resource globally, is essential for various human needs, and its sustainable management is crucial due to the increasing demand and uneven distribution. The study identifies groundwater potential zones by integrating thematic layers such as soil type, slope, land use, and drainage patterns using ArcGIS software. The results indicate that approximately 70% of the study area falls under excellent, good, or moderate groundwater potential zones, while 30% is classified as poor or very poor. These findings are essential for guiding groundwater recharge structures and conservation efforts. Additionally, the study employs a slope analysis that reveals how different soil types and slope classes affect water retention and runoff. The research highlights the utility of GIS and RS in water resource management, allowing for targeted interventions in regions with varying groundwater potential. This approach provides a valuable framework for sustainable water management, particularly in semi-arid regions like the Bindusara Watershed, where rainfall variability significantly impacts groundwater quality. The integration of various datasets enables more informed decision-making for local stakeholders involved in watershed management and land use planning.

Keywords: Groundwater potential zones, Geographic Information Systems (GIS), Remote Sensing (RS), Bindusara Watershed, Groundwater recharge, Thematic layers, Soil type, Slope analysis, Drainage patterns

I. INTRODUCTION

The most essential resource for life is fresh water. Water is required for drinking, sanitation, agriculture, manufacturing, and a variety of other activities. Although water is the most plentiful material in the natural world, it is not distributed equally across the globe. In contrast to diminishing supplies, worldwide water demand is increasing. The biggest requirement of human civilisation today is drinking water. The value of current water will only rise as the population of water-scarce regions grows. Water is the main resource that controls the economy, development, and progress of a region, state, or country as the population grows. From alcohol to sanitation, and from industry to agricultural growth, water is the main resource that controls the economy, development, and progress of a region, state, or country. Our community's growth is dependent on the availability and usage of sufficient water. This priceless resource is in short supply at times, plentiful at others, and equally dispersed throughout space and time. Groundwater is the world's second biggest freshwater source, accounting

for 30% of global freshwater resources. Groundwater is the source of drinking water for more than 1.5 billion people across the globe. Rain replenishes groundwater, which then interacts with surface water. As it interacts with the ground, rain, rivers, and other natural water sources artificially refill it. In many tropical nations, groundwater is the primary source of water. Groundwater is readily available and devoid of the pollutants found in surface water. Humans, on the other hand, often abuse groundwater resources. Due to a lack of knowledge regarding groundwater resources, we are unable to make full use of them. Groundwater management will take precedence in this situation. The distribution of groundwater throughout the globe varies based on climate conditions and reservoir features. Groundwater is the most important source of water, and in certain dry regions, it is the only one. Reservoirs are where this fossil is kept. It also explains the widespread use of groundwater for human water supply, which can meet more than 60% of human needs in many parts of the world. Rain and surface water, usually through porous layers, usually give high quality groundwater; it also explains the widespread use of groundwater for human water supply, which can meet more than 60% of human needs in many parts of the world.

Groundwater is water trapped under the ground surface in soil pores and fractures in rock formations. A reservoir is formed when a unit or unit deposit of rock generates groundwater that may be utilized under natural circumstances. The depth to which the gaps, fractures, and voids in the soil holes in the rock are fully saturated with water is known as the water table. Natural discharge frequently occurs near the shores and seas, creating oasis or wetlands, and replenishes groundwater. Extraction wells are a popular way to extract groundwater for agricultural, municipal, and industrial uses.

Fig 1. Watershed

The creation and execution of strategies, programs, and projects to manage and enhance watershed activities impacting the flora, wildlife, and human population along the watershed boundary is known as watershed management. It is not about managing natural resources; it is about controlling human actions that have an effect on those resources. The river's drainage basin serves as a natural barrier to human-environmental interaction management and minimization. Because human activities include the acts of government, towns, businesses, and landlords, watershed management is really a collaborative endeavor. Community water shortages, poor water quality, floods, and erosion may all be avoided with effective watershed management. The cost of maintaining a watershed is much less than the expense of future remediation. Land and water are critical components for agricultural growth and drinking water supply. As a consequence of increasing population growth, urbanization, industry, and agriculture, water consumption has skyrocketed. The monsoons are critical to India's agricultural

economy. People are resorting to groundwater independently rather than recharging owing to inadequate rainfall in the past 3-4 years, resulting in groundwater levels below 100-200 meters. Maharashtra's current drought is worst hydrologically than it was in 1972. The causes for this unusual scenario include the building of huge dams, soggy agricultural patterns, disregard of local water systems, and reckless water management. Big dams, according to the former planning commissioner, are not the answer to Maharashtra's water issues. Despite the acute water scarcity, tanker owners in Maharashtra's Jalna have spent more than Rs. The water industry is flourishing in drought-stricken Marathwada, with over 6 million transactions. To decrease dependence on thermal plants and supply them with precious water, the state should look into alternative energy sources. Despite the present availability of sufficient food grains, the scarcity of drinking water is still extremely severe when compared to the 1972 drought. As a consequence of recent research sponsored by the International Development Research Center, new technologies and natural resource management (NRM) models have developed in the case of watersheds (IDRC). Watershed initiatives supported by the IDRC have achieved major advancements in integrating collaborative and multidisciplinary research, building NRM resilience organizations, and enhancing broad-based impact methods and approaches. Promoted. The main findings from IDRC's Latin American and Asian Minga and Community-Based Natural Resource Management (CBNRM) Program Initiative Studies are summarized in this document. An in-depth examination of project results came through individual interviews and contacts with IDRC researchers and partners, as well as individual researchers. Because of their biophysical and, in most instances, social features, watersheds are suitable units for NRMs. The interrelationships between significant natural resources and human activities are highlighted in watersheds. Reservoirs, for example, are important data collecting and modeling units in water management. Water, which links various owners via upstream-downstream streams, is the main resource that determines the borders of a watershed. These flows have the capacity to foster collaboration across political and cultural divides, as well as to unite activity at many levels, while also raising the danger of conflict. Second, in watershed management, land use is a critical consideration. Soil quality and water content are affected by the intensity of land use for agricultural and human activities. Water quality in rural regions is threatened by non-point-source pollution from intense agriculture, animal activity, and human waste. Increased floods, soil erosion, and reduced reservoir recharge are all factors that contribute to deforestation.

Recognized as a key decision maker for livelihood and watershed management in feudal, private and religious activities. CPR (Common Asset Resource) is important, especially for those with low incomes. Women are the primary users of CPR and are well versed in CPR interactions and management practices, so removing women from decision-making power is an important barrier to successful management. Third, interdisciplinary research is needed on the complex interrelationships of human and resource dynamics in watersheds. Projects with a great degree of biophysical and socio-economic research are the most effective in all aspects of the project. They need to realize that multiple actors are important and should try to include research at all stages to ensure that the research is applied and that the management system is sustainable in the long run. Local stakeholders need to be involved in the research process, set goals and see to it that the results are put into practice. Also, reliable datasets and collection methods are required to initiate comprehensive watershed research. Combining

collaborative research with rigorous, reliable data for modeling can be challenging. Researchers need to define their functions and goals as well as the procedural implications of the organizational structure, as research is largely action-oriented. In-depth study of gender and power dynamics in society has led to many successes in this area besides promoting participation and competence. Fourth, effective integrated watershed management requires effective communication and coordination as well as research, decision making and multi-step action. The foundation for developing a shared local resource management and watershed-scale participatory approach is democratic local government. Small programs that achieve group standards that promote cooperation and democratic processes at all levels are set as long-term goals. Scaling up, providing thorough support and developing a comprehensive plan In the most effective scaling efforts, all manufacturing components are used. Cooperative mechanisms such as pay for the RPE should be considered within political boundaries.

It is important to know what level of integration is needed to successfully manage a resource or issue, so that any discussion of the scale does not become too complicated. Finally, effective integrated watershed management requires the participation of strong organizations that can bridge the gap between local applied research and broader policy considerations. Instead of creating parallel, competitive processes, initiatives are most successful in building these organizations when significant efforts are made to include relevant government agencies in research projects and management programs. The most successful company for shared watershed management is the Multi-Share Platform. They come in a variety of shapes and sizes, doing a wide variety of tasks, from simple consultation to actual decision making. Such forums are difficult to set up and maintain, but they are not detrimental to shared management. On the other hand, these forums can provide legal space for discussion, conflict resolution, and planning that are often not available in existing organizations. There should be protections along with such forums to prevent local elites from interfering and to ensure that all important stakeholders have an equal voice and participation. Watershed management companies need to adapt to rapid changes in the social and biological environment. Developing local links and links to research resources across the country is key to the long-term sustainability of a research project. Further research is needed in many areas: Watershed Management Software and Rural Watershed Management Environment and Human Health (Pollution and Unknown Source Resources) on the Environment, Impact of Complex Connections Impact of Complex Relationships on Estimating Public Impact Resources for Watersheds Management And develop better methods for combining socio-economic data. Understanding the interaction between surface and groundwater Management of watersheds means maintenance of watersheds. The long-term tendency to make data sharing decisions at the watershed level in research involves multi-sectoral efforts at multiple levels. Despite its complexity and challenges, it provides the most effective foundation for NRM. Developing expertise requires the participation of the best and most diverse stakeholders in many areas of study. One of the lessons gained from the shortcomings of centrally planned watershed development projects was that local people were compelled to resort to terrace, bunding, distocking, and other technologies, or to confront the ideas of foreign specialists. As it is (idb). As a consequence, cooperation limits and subsidies are feasible, allowing for more effective and long-term development of watersheds. All watershed stockholders - consumers, politicians, academics, and others - must realize that partnerships are more than simply another method to offer technological answers if they are to be effective. A

significant change in thinking about sustainable watershed management theory and practice demands a commitment to a participatory approach. Shareholders in a partnership are expected to work together continuously on management, establishing criteria, prioritizing, assessing possible solutions, suggesting technologies and techniques, and monitoring and evaluating outcomes. Watershed management research, technology, organizational innovations, and the extension of the research agenda all benefit from customer engagement. Consumers' active involvement in the research process is evident in their contributions to setting priorities, assessing technology, and tracking outcomes. The role of resource consumers in watershed management and research is examined in this article. Part 2 explains why participatory watershed management is important and highlights key research problems that may emerge as a consequence of user involvement. Part 3 explores how various participatory research concepts may be used to various aspects of the watershed study. Section 4 presents some empirical data on how participatory methods are currently being used in watershed management research projects, as well as potential obstacles to maximizing and coordinating their usage. A summary and conclusion end the fifth part.

Why is it that watershed management is done by participants in the first place? Early soil and water conservation initiatives in the United States, East Africa, and South Asia supported restricted technology such as terraces and contour dams to avoid soil erosion. Two important assumptions underpin the development of such programs. The first is that soil conservation techniques are universal; what works in one location will also work in another. The second hypothesis is that local farmers are totally ignorant of the cutbacks, as well as their origins and consequences (Sundar and Shah, 1999). Both estimates are often misrepresented. When it comes to local farming systems, program technologies are often inadequate in terms of environment and economy, especially in terms of labor availability. In addition, people are being pressured as a means of preventing erosion, rather than perfecting them in areas where local soil and water management practices have been used. These centralized soil and water conservation schemes often lead to more or less erosion because new buildings are not maintained or are technically inferior (Sunder and Shaw, 1999; Ker et al. 1996).). Unfortunately, many current watershed development programs that are successors to previous large-scale soil and water conservation programs still have similar expectations. According to Farrington and Lobo (1997), watershed development is a high priority in India, with 99% of watershed development projects still using traditional methods, with a focus on physical design rather than local economic, social and environmental issues. Depending on the circumstances. Farmers and other clients are less involved in project planning, but they are more active in watershed development programs (Hinkliff et al. 1999; Farrington et al. 1999). These programs aim to improve the appropriateness of resource management techniques and approaches promoted by projects by collecting inputs from customers about resource constraints, the integrity of existing resource management practices, and their standards for potential new technologies.

Because of the biophysical processes that interact with each other, watershed development is more than just a summation of different patches of land and water currents, and individual farmers are not the only ones taking steps to increase production on specific plots. Watershed management takes into account not only the interactions of individual plots in time and space, but also common pool resources, including forests, waterfalls, alleys, roads and footpaths, and vegetation along rivers and streams

(Swallow et al. 2000). Take into account. Watershed resources provide different services to different customers and resource utilization choices affect these customers in different ways. In shared watershed management, shareholders often have a joint discussion process that defines their interests, sets priorities, evaluates options, and monitors tools and outcomes. Watershed management emphasizes the control and direction of land, water and other natural resources. Natural resources in watersheds are used to produce appropriate products and services while minimizing the impact on soil and watershed resources. These connections include socioeconomic, human-institutional and bio-physical interactions between soil, water and land use, as well as ground-groundwater connections (Ffolliott et al. 2002). In short, the Watershed Basic Organizing Unit is responsible for resource management. Watershed management has been around since 2000 BC (Zheng 2004; Chen 2007), and it continues to grow and improve over time. Watershed Management is a broad term that encompasses a wide range of activities "the study of the relevant features of Watershed with the aim of continuously distributing its resources, plans, programs and activities aimed at improving watershed performance affecting plants and animals." Comprehensive watershed management practice has gained popularity as a result of the development of "development and implementation processes of projects and human communities" across the watershed border. Fundamentals of Watershed Management (German et al. 2007) uses integrated watershed management for various integration with environmental, social and economic goals as well as social, technological and organizational purposes. Elements. The result of this combination is a "creative, comprehensive, multi-resource management planning process that balances healthy environmental, economic and cultural / social conditions. This allows for land and water planning integrity. Identifies and prepares for water, plant, animal and human land use interactions "(Red Deer River Watershed Alliance 2015).

1.1 Objectives

1. Collection of data (DEM, Soil strata maps, Rainfall data) for the selected site.
2. Watershed delineation for the proposed site on Bindusara River.
3. Overlaying the Bindusara basin over the soil strata map and selecting the feasible sites for groundwater recharge by considering the slopes of terrain at those locations.
4. Suggesting a site for water infrastructure like groundwater recharge wells in the Bindusara River watershed.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section contains a literature overview and review. How much groundwater flows under the earth's surface is an important issue in hydrogeology. It is critical to comprehend the infiltration routes taken by surface water. Infiltrated water may follow subterranean channels and quickly mingle with the flow, known as interflow or surface flow in this instance. Intrusive water may also get into deep groundwater, which can last for a long time.

The best method at the moment is to systematize data of any topographical characteristics, analyze inter-disciplinary, inter-class dependency and variability, and analyze the cumulative effect on groundwater development. This is shown by integrating background data on the aforementioned

subjects into a GIS for assessment utilizing remote sensing techniques and multi-scale decision procedures.

Liu Laixing et al. is the author of the paper entitled "Research on geospatial information sharing platform based on Arc-GIS server", It serves as a user handbook and provides instructions for using the Arc-GIS program. This presentation went through numerous geological structures, folds, faults, terrain conditions, and Arc-GIS technologies. The use of Arc-GIS in determining geomorphological characteristics and different topographic conditions in the form of thematic maps, which can be utilized to efficiently manage watersheds, was also addressed. Linfang Ding et al. in his paper named, "Comparative study of thematic mapping and scientific visualization", He compares several key features of theme mapping and scientific visualization in his paper "The Comparative Study of Thematic Mapping and Scientific Visualization." They include purpose, data source, geo-reference, data processing, taxonomy, and icon for various background maps. Linfang Ding L. demonstrated how to create textures, shapes, forms, drainage patterns, and various background maps in vegetation using effective techniques. Tajinder Kaur et al. Under the heading of Drinking and Irrigation using Hydrochemical Studies in Punjab, India, in the southwestern part of the Malwa region, sheds light on groundwater quality and compares its suitability for drinking and irrigation purposes in the Malwa region. The highest cultivated area in Punjab, which uses a lot of pesticides and fertilizers, is assessing groundwater quality for purposes. Twenty-four groundwater samples were collected and analyzed for almost all important cations, ions, and other physicochemical properties. The results of the physico-chemical test revealed that the majority of the samples exceeded the Indian standards' allowable limits. Rajat C. et al. An effective technique for the development of groundwater in arid climates was created in the article "Remote Sensing and GIS for Groundwater Mapping and Identification," as well as the recharge capability of a site to predict water interactions through artificial recharge structures. There is recompense. The study concludes, "The goal of the research is to map groundwater and identify artificial recharge sites using remote sensing and GIS." Involved in the making of important decisions. Areas and locations that could be used have been identified. Groundwater development in arid areas can be accomplished with the proposed technology. As a consequence, comments such as physical functions and aerial photos prefer to limit site measurements to a few. Dams, leak tanks, gabion structures, recharge wells / ditches, and other artificial recharge structures are all tested for capacity. Y. Srinivasa Rao et al. The Chittoor area, which is made up of hard rock terrain and is situated in the drought-prone state of Andhra Pradesh, India, was examined. Tone, texture, size, form, slope, drainage pattern, and vegetation are all interpreted using RS and GIS technologies. Field investigations were performed to determine the location of wells, well yield, water table, and the collection of water samples for hardness, TDS, fluoride, and magnesium concentration analyses. According to their research, the quality of Chittoor's ground water would deteriorate owing to contamination from poorly handled industrial effluents and municipal sewage. To address this, corrective measures such as putting limitations on businesses and municipalities for appropriate effluent and waste treatment are suggested.

B. S. Chaudhary et al. Using the GIS program ARC-GIS, they built a model to determine the groundwater potential zones of the Kaushalya-Jhajhara Watershed in India. Various geology, geomorphology, slope, drainage density, and LULC thematic layers have been created and given

appropriate weightages and rankings. These layers were used to generate ground water potential zones using a weightage overlay technique in GIS software. Planners and decision makers working on water resource development plans will benefit greatly from the integration of different maps. This contemporary approach is very helpful for preparing environmental development plans for watershed development. S. K. Nag et al. Using remote sensing and GIS methods, developed a model to identify groundwater potential regions. Dwarkeshwar Watershed, Bankura District, West Bengal is the study area. For combined analysis of multiclass maps, this research employs a simple and easy weighted overlay technique. The efficacy of this technique is examined as part of the human judgment analysis. A parameter's weight reflects its relative significance. Groundwater potential regions have been described using weighted sequencing, which takes into consideration three factors as well as the hydrogeomorphic conditions of the area, hydrogeomorphology, and linear density. They came to the conclusion that when the land use in the watershed varies through time and place, the variables influencing the watershed's hydrological response vary as well. It is essential to understand Watershed's present groundwater conditions in order to determine the effect of future land use change on its groundwater resources. As a result, determining the degree to which water resources have been altered is necessary. Rainfall, surface, and subsurface conditions are all hydrological variables that influence land use change. Land use change is thought to be influenced by rainfall. The geological structure of quartz, schist, and slate in their research region reveals a fine structure of drainage patterns, suggesting a significant groundwater potential. In the Dwarakeshwar catchment region, linement, hydro-geomorphology, and **** important factors in groundwater occurrence were studied. The final map was designed as a potential map to provide local governments and planners direct information about regions suited for groundwater research. M. Nagarajan et al. has completed a research named "Assessment of Groundwater Potential Zones Using GIS Technique" to identify groundwater potential zones using remote sensing and GIS. The goal of this research was to use Kattankulathurblock's thematic maps to locate groundwater potential zones. GIS was utilized to create a database using spatial and other data, as well as a base map, drainage map, watershed map, geomorphology map, groundwater table map, and groundwater infiltration map in this research. This map was used to develop a groundwater potential zones map by determining relationships between different factors and integrating the aforementioned data. Based on the examination of the different topics stated above, it is concluded that this research is beneficial in improving groundwater levels and preventing future depletion. This research was also useful in determining the placement of an artificial recharge structure. R. Al-Ruzouq et al. have discussed for finding out the good quality ground water for UAE which belong to mostly desert stretch in paper "Geomatics for mapping of groundwater potential zones in northern part of the United Arab Emiratis - Sharjah city". The DTM (Digital Terrain Model) may be used to efficiently demarcate watersheds and generate stream networks and flow directions. Their research shows how to estimate GWPZ using GIS and photogrammetric techniques. The weights in this research were calculated based on a literature analysis and domain knowledge.

Ram Avtar et al. had studied effect of interlinking of Ken-Betwa river on the ground water potential zones is discussed effectively in the paper "Identification and analysis of groundwater potential zones in Ken-Betwa river linking area using remote sensing and geographic information system". The research compares the GWP zones for the months of May, June, July, August, and March during a

five-year period from 1999 to 2004. The GPZ of the previous five years is compared, and appropriate conclusions are calculated for water conservation and recharge structure estimation. Their research aids in the identification of groundwater depletion zones in the Bundelkhand region, as well as the placement of artificial recharge facilities. Pankaj Kumar et al. The Kilinochchi Basin in northern Sri Lanka has been studied for potential groundwater shortage regions. IRS-IC LISS III satellite data, Landsat TM digital, and SRTM data were used to generate geomorphological, geological, drainage density, and liniment density maps. The proportionate contribution of each background map to the groundwater potential determines the weight of each background map. On each background map, each feature is also assessed. The groundwater potential index was calculated using ground control points on all backdrop maps and then integrated into the GIS in phases using a generalized aggregation technique. Groundwater potential regions will be identified based on this final expectation and grade. They discovered that using a combined strategy of remote sensing and GIS technologies, they were able to effectively identify groundwater in the research region. Excellent, very good, good, moderate, and poor are the five categories of groundwater potential zones. N. S. Mangesh et al. Precipitation, flow, drainage density, soil, and other cooperating factors were investigated, as well as their relationships. He provided suggestions for comparing and weighting various factors. Background maps of lithology, drainage soils, and other topics were created using SOI topsheet data and satellite photos. Each of these maps is assigned points using the impact factor approach. All of these strata were counted in order to get groundwater, and the regions were categorized as very poor, poor, medium, good, and very excellent. M. Gupta et al. In the steep terrain of the Pavagarh area, an effort was undertaken to locate groundwater potential zones. They described the appropriate technique for water conservation and erosion prevention in rocky and difficult terrain. Hilly regions with high rainfall, slope, drainage density, and moderate forest cover, as well as typical hard rock terrain. As a result, appropriate weight supply is critical; large weight values are given for low slope areas and poor drainage surfaces. Nancy Johnson et al. Consumer participation affects watershed management studies, according to the research "User Participation in Watershed Management and Research." It broadens the collaborative research agenda to include new topics including organizational behavior, collective action, and conflict resolution, as well as a shift in technology and practice development and delivery. This will need further research on locality and watershed management problems, starting with a synthesis and comparison of previous experience in areas like boundary and size, facility transaction costs, and building indicators. Partnership management, which is not closely connected to research - it is regarded a knowledge creation process that supports technological and organizational development - is often hampered by a lack of suitable technical choices, information, and organizations.

Monika Saini, et al. Examines the paper "Measuring the Impact of Watershed Management Programs on the Watershed Community's Livelihood." The SLA employed in this study can objectively evaluate the impacts of watershed management on the community's livelihood. From before WW to before WMP, livelihood in the Lakshmipura Watershed improved. They also discovered that the watershed community's livelihood has improved significantly in terms of capital. These benefits are mainly due to the therapies employed during WMP. Capital Assets Evaluation Quantitative Livelihood Assessment In assessing such development initiatives, this approach is very useful. This method

enables you to keep track of livelihoods at several levels. The subsistence score may be computed using the respondents' general average approach, which takes into account socioeconomic status, property ranking, land size, caste system, village, and watershed level. This approach may also be used to design a watershed management plan during the implementation of WMP. Quantitative evaluation of subsistence capital aids in the prioritization of watershed management activities and the development of capital-oriented solutions. This approach also aids in program monitoring and assessment, as well as providing valuable feedback for future program growth and better program design. Dr. (Mrs.) Hansa Shukla, The research of "Watershed Management: Its Role in Environmental Planning and Management" ends the report. Integrated approach: This method entails the integration of technology within the drainage area's natural limits for the optimum development of land, water, and plant resources in order to satisfy humans and animals' fundamental requirements in a sustainable manner. The goal of this strategy is to raise ordinary people's living conditions by improving their earning potential and giving all of the necessary facilities for proper production (Singh, 2000). Integrated watershed management, land and water conservation techniques, water collection and groundwater recharge in ponds, enhanced water resource efficiency and crop diversity, better seed usage, integrated nutrition management, and integration were all achieved. Methods of rot management, etc. Government Policy: - Primary stakeholders, government and non-government organizations, and other entities are all involved in coalition policy, which deals with collective action and community involvement. Watershed management requires a diverse set of skills and talents. Important factors include easy access and timely guidance to farmers on how to monitor the impacts of watersheds. It increases farmer awareness and improves their capacity to reach out to the appropriate individuals when issues occur. Engineering, agricultural science, forestry, horticulture, animal husbandry, entomology, sociology, economics, and marketing are among the skills required. It is not always feasible to get all of the necessary assistance and expertise at a company. As a result, to optimize the efficacy of different watershed initiatives and interventions, the consortium method draws in experts from a range of disciplines. R. Ramesh, R. Purvaja, A. Lakshmi, A. Newton, H.H. Kremer and J. Weichselgartner et.al. LOICZ Global Change Assessment and Synthesis of River Catchment - Coastal Sea Interactions and Human Dimensions" was studied. Erosion and sedimentation. Pollution and hunger have also been discovered. This research is interested in the effect of human civilization on physical motions along the shore, such as water, sediment, nutrients, heavy metals, and man-made pollution. DPSIR matrices were created utilizing expert knowledge gathered from workshop presentations and discussions focused on different causes, pressures, state changes, and effects on rivers up to the shore. The LOICZ basin approach offers an in-depth evaluation of key natural processes and coastal states influenced by natural and human pressures to examine river basin-based coastal alterations. Due to energy exchange, sedimentation, and water flow, as well as biodiversity, coastal regions for human settlement, rest, and the whole south, rivers and their downstream areas play an essential role in coastal development. Asia's and the world's economic activity Anupriya, Lalit R. Chamat, Lalit Chamat et.al. has studied the topic and concluded in the report, "Using a Geographic Information System (GIS) and Quantum-GIS, researchers investigated the interconnection of rivers. " We looked at the Vidarbha area, which has a lot of water, as part of the research. Water storage is expected to be lower at lower altitudes than at higher elevations. It is relatively simple to establish how

the rivers are linked using hydrological data from the research region and tributary rivers. It will be considerably simpler to carry water to the lower regions if there is more water in the highlands. On the height map, appropriate routes should be drawn. It will be simpler to evaluate the project based on how it is constructed. This information is extremely helpful for administrative authorities who may use it to plan the building of check dams, reservoirs, and seepage tanks to enhance water supply in the studied region. Analyzing such an environmental issue with this software is a significant step forward. The fundamental concept behind linking the river is to supply water to a region that has a year-round water deficit. This river interlinking project's idea is to transfer some water from rivers to dry rivers with large rivers. Carmine Covelli, This paper's research case is the Comstra River basin, which is connected to the Besanto River's biggest basin. The location is in the southern Italian province of Basilicata. This choice is based on the area's environmental sensitivity and the availability of a large amount of data that may be utilized to validate the method described in this paper. Its terrain is mostly . The remainder of the region is made up of soils with varying lithologies inherited from clay soils with limestone and loose clay deposits, sand, and complex rocks. The primary goal of this research was to change the RUSLE model factors. Corrections focused on length and angle (LS-factor) were originally found as the most essential factors in estimating soil damage from erosion. Belayneh Bufebo, Studies a report entitled "Shenkola Watershed, Land Use / Land Cover Change and Its Driving Forces in South Central Ethiopia". Forest acreage decreases and agricultural land increases. Agricultural land increased from 70.49 per cent in 1973 to 79.48 per cent in 2017, while forest land fell from 29.51 per cent in 1973 to 20.52 per cent in 2017. The main reason for LU / LC change is agricultural development, policy change and social unrest, population. Stress, scarcity of agricultural land and biophysical causes. Climate change, loss of biodiversity, loss of basic forest products, habitat change, declining quality and water availability and declining agricultural yields are all effects of LU / LC change. Expansion of agricultural land at the expense of forest in the Shenkola catchment area has a detrimental effect on the natural resources and livelihoods of the local people. Consequently, appropriate measures must be implemented to mitigate significant changes in land use and to align environmental protection with human livelihoods.

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for the study is described in this chapter, along with a conceptual framework that outlines a comprehensive approach to doing the research. It comprises GIS software for data gathering, geographical and other auxiliary data processing with remote sensing, and thematic map creation. This is followed by overlapping for multi-scale analysis and the creation of an overall map indicating possible groundwater regions. Using GIS, this research tries to characterize the possible groundwater potential regions of the Bindusara Watershed in Maharashtra's Beed District. Groundwater studies are becoming more essential not only for identifying prospective groundwater areas, but also for monitoring, preserving, and protecting these key natural critical resources as a measure of changes in water quality indicators during and after the rainy season. Are also being looked into.

3.1 Topography and Drainage

The watershed's topography is 598 meters high, with a maximum height of at least 481 meters above sea level. The study area is sloping from south to northeast in general. Geographic differences may be seen in the terrain of the research region. The Bindusara River, a tributary of the Godavari River, is

fed by minor streams throughout the basin. The employment of a water control structure in the main, submine, (or occasionally lateral) duct to prolong the drainage outlet to different depths is known as drainage water management. Farmers will have greater control over drainage as a result of this. Benefits of Potential Yield: Crop yields may be improved beyond the typical crop response to drainage with proper organized management and timely rains. Field research on the agricultural advantages of learning, on the other hand, are few and incomplete. A drainage pattern is a pattern created by streams, rivers, and lakes in a drainage basin. The patterns created by stream erosion reflect the kinds of rocks in the environment and the geological features of running streams throughout time. Drainage patterns are influenced by the earth's topography, its , and the particular region of hard or soft rocks.

Types of Drainage Patterns

Based on the shape and formation of river patterns, there are different drainage patterns. Broadly it is classified into two types –

1. Discordant Drainage pattern
2. Concordant Drainage pattern

The nation is divided into four natural regions by landforms and drainage: north, east, center, and south. Despite being physically part of the Central Plains, Bangkok's metropolitan region, which includes the country's capital and biggest metropolis, is treated as a distinct entity in other ways. The population, basic resources, natural characteristics, and degree of social and economic development of each of the four geographical regions vary from the others. The physical layout of Thailand's physical structure is characterized by its variety of areas. In the winter, the hilly north offers cold enough temperatures for lychee and strawberry production. Steep river basins and mountains that encircle these high summits border the center plain.

3.2 Soil

Melting of the earth, atmosphere, and rocks produces this substance. This is a time-consuming procedure. Various mechanical, chemical, and biological processes induce weathering and disintegration. The soil also aids in the retention of water in its pores, which helps to prevent soil erosion and preserve groundwater levels. The kind of soil in the region has an impact on groundwater infiltration. The National Bureau of Soil Surveys classifies various kinds of soils on the planet based on their properties and textures (NBSS).

In soil, organic materials, minerals, gases, liquids, and organisms all have a role in sustaining life. The pedosphere serves four primary purposes:

- Plants use it as a growth medium.
- As a way of storing, delivering, and purifying water
- On the globe, there is a climate shift.
- Organisms' habitat

All of these actions altered the structure and characteristics of the soil.

Some scientific definitions differentiate soil from dust by restricting the previous word to displaced clay; some scientific definitions distinguish soil from dust by limiting the previous term to displaced clay. The lithosphere, hydrosphere, atmosphere, and biosphere all interact with the pedosphere. The word pedolith refers to the mineral and organic materials (clay matrix) from ancient soils, as well as

the solid and porous phases of the original stone. Gases (soil atmosphere) and water are present (soil solution). As a result, soil scientists may conceive of it as a three-state system made up of solids, liquids, and gases. Climate, soil, fauna, and soil parent material (basic minerals) all have an impact on the mitigation of interactions through time, as can factors such as height, direction, and topography. The tributary erosion environment, for example, is continuously changing owing to different physical, chemical, and biological processes. Because of its complexity and deep interrelationships, soil ecologists consider it to be an ecosystem. Most soils have a dry bulk density of 1.1 to 1.6 g/cm³ (taking into account the density of the soil when dried), however the density of soil particles is very high, ranging between 2.6 and 2.7 g/cm³. The smallest continent on the planet is older than the Pleistocene and no older than the Cenozoic, despite the fact that fossil soils are mostly preserved up to the Archean.

Figure 3.1 Soil

Figure 3.2 Topography

3.3 Land Use and Land Cover

Organic matter, minerals, gases, liquids and organisms all sustain life in soil. The pedosphere has four main functions:

As a growing substrate for plants

As a method of storing, supplying and purifying water

As a climate change agent on the planet,

Habitats of organisms

All these activities changed the structure and properties of the soil.

Soil is sometimes known as earth or dirt, and some scientific definitions differentiate it from dust by restricting the former word to displaced clay.

The lithosphere, hydrosphere, atmosphere, and biosphere all interact with the pedosphere. The word pedolith refers to the mineral and organic materials (clay matrix) from ancient soils, as well as the solid and porous phases of the original stone. Gases (soil atmosphere) and water are present (soil solution). As a result, soil scientists may think of soil as a three-state system made up of solids, liquids, and gases.

One of the remote sensing applications for land use is natural resource management.

Conservation of wildlife habitat

For GIS input, create a baseline map.

Expansion and occupancy of cities

Seismic / exploration / resource extraction activity routing and logistical planning

Illustration of Damage (Tornado, Flood, Volcano, Earthquake, Fire)

Law imposes tax and property value limitations.

Landing strips, highways, clearings, bridges, and land/water interfaces are all targets to be identified.

The words land use and land cover, on the other hand, are often used interchangeably, each having its own meaning. The surface covering of plant, urban infrastructure, water, bare soil, and so on is known as land cover. Land cover identification is the starting point for operations like thematic mapping and change analysis. Land use refers to how land is used, such as for recreation, animal habitat, or agriculture.

The phrases land use / land cover (LULC) and land use / land cover (LULC) relate to the categorization of human activities and natural components through time when used together. Methods. a source of information

3.2 Study Area

Location map showing the boundaries of the study area and study area map showing various administrative features are depicted as per below figure. Watershed is located in Beed District. Watershed ranges from latitude 583356o N and longitude 2095700o E to latitude 557596o N and longitude 2083933o E. Watershed contributing to Bindusara River which is tributary of Godavari river. The study area falls in the semi-arid zone of Beed.

3.3 Data Collection

The spatial data requirement consists of DEM of study area, satellite image, hydrological data, and ground water level data of study area, water quality standards and different maps provided by respective department.

1) DEM Tiles: - Cartosat-1 Digital elevation model (DEM) data was collected Bhuvan website
Source: <http://bhuvan.nrsc.gov.in>

2) Rainfall Data- Obtain from official website of Govt. of Maharashtra: www.maharain.gov.in

3) Soil Maps: - Soil Maps provided by National Bureau of Soil Survey (NBSS)

3.3 Basic of Remote Sensing and Geographic Information System

The basic concept of Remote Sensing (RS) and Geographical information system (GIS) is explained are expressed as follows

Remote Sensing

The art and science of making planetary observations using sensors aboard an airplane or satellite is known as remote sensing. These sensors gather data in the form of pictures, which they may then modify, analyze, and display. Remote sensing is a method of assessing and collecting data about an item or event without having to come into close touch with it. Remote sensing images are incorporated in the GIS. Data may be obtained in areas that are inaccessible to the public, such as volcanoes and ocean depths, using remote sensing. Remote sensing is the recovery of data without the use of an item or a phenomenon, as well as without on-site examination of the site or physical interaction with the topic.

Researchers may use to observe El Nio and other natural long-term and short-term phenomena by utilizing orbiting platforms to gather and transmit data from various regions of the electromagnetic spectrum. It's possible to utilize. It is possible to include it. The information has been given. Air traffic control, early warning, and large-scale weather information are all common uses for radar. enforcement for improved weather forecasting and border monitoring, and rainfall conditions and severity. Another kind of active collecting in the ionosphere is plasma. The use of interferometric synthetic apertures to create accurate radar landscape digital elevation models is common. Satellite altimeters, as well as laser and radar altimeters, offer a wealth of information. They detect gravity-induced water swelling to map seawater characteristics. guns are the most common name for projectiles. Although LIDAR is used to detect and compute chemical concentrations in the atmosphere, aerial LIDAR may be used to estimate the height and characteristics of objects on Earth instead of radar technology. LIDAR is mostly used for vegetation remote sensing. Radiometers and photometers, which collect the radiation reflected and emitted by various frequencies, are the most frequently used instruments.

Fig.3.3 Shows Processing of Sensors in RS

The interaction between incident radiation and interest targets is involved in this process. The usage of an imaging system with the following seven components is an example of this. Remote sensing, on the other hand, detects radiated energy using non-imaging sensors.

1. Energy source or illumination - The initial need of remote sensing is an energy source that illuminates or delivers electromagnetic energy to an energy target.
2. Radiation and the Environment - As energy moves from its source to its destination, it interacts with the atmosphere. A second touch may occur when the energy passes from the target to the sensor.
3. Interaction with the target- After passing through the environment, the energy interacts with the target, which is determined by the radiation target as well as the radiation characteristics.
4. Energy recording by sensor- Once the energy has been dissipated or released from the target, a sensor is required to capture and record the electromagnetic radiation (remotely - not attached to the target).
4. Transmission, Reception, and Processing - The energy measured by the sensor is often sent electronically to a receiving and processing unit, where the data is transformed into an image (hardcopy and/or digital).
6. Analysis and Commentary - The processed picture is presented and/or digitally or electronically retrieved in order to acquire information about the published subject.
7. Application - The remote sensing procedure is complete when we are able to better comprehend an issue, discover new facts, or collect information from pictures. Complete an application.

From start to end, these seven components encompass the whole remote sensing process. We will look at them all in the fifth chapter of this lesson, based on what we've studied. Have fun on your trip!

Fig.3.4 Shows Processing of RS Data in GIS tool

Geographic Information System

Water quality can be assessed, water availability can be calculated, floods can be avoided, the natural environment can be better understood, and water resource problems may be addressed using GIS. It is extensively used in infrastructure, water resource management, environmental management, spatial analysis, and regional urban development planning as a decision-making or auxiliary tool. Environmental and natural resource management information systems that are more data available, simpler to integrate, and adaptive to environmental and natural decision-making requirements have emerged as a consequence of GIS development.

Fig.3.5 Shows Interrelation of GIS and RS

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Ground Water Potential Zones

Depending upon the groundwater potentiality, each class of the thematic layers are reclassified based on its infiltration capacity and roughly placed into one group. Following thematic maps were generated for integration in Arc-GIS under weightage overlay tool and the result of integration is obtained is given below in above fig.4.1.

Map

Geomorphological map

Ground map

Map of land usage and land cover

Map of drainage density

Density of lineage map

Map of Rainfall

Map of groundwater levels

After assigning the ranking and weightage to various attributes in each of the themes as stated in table 4.7 above and running the weighted overlay analysis in ArcGIS software, following groundwater potential zone map was obtained, which clearly indicates 5 types of groundwater zone viz. excellent,

good, moderate, poor and very poor from groundwater potential point of view. The area under each zone is given in the table 4.1, which is as follows

Table No. 1 Details of Ground Water Potential Zones

Groundwater potential zone	Area under zone (in Sq. Km.)	% of total area
Excellent	4.63	18.75
Good	6.69	22.28
Moderate	8.67	28.88
Poor	6.12	20.38
Very Poor	2.91	9.71
Total	30.02	100

This According to this research, topography, soil, land use, and drainage are the primary determinants of groundwater quality. This map depicts the total area of each study region as a percentage of the overall study area: excellent (18.75%), good (22.28%), moderate (28.88%), bad (20.38%), and extremely poor (9.71 percent). The majority of the research region is divided into excellent, good, and medium zones, indicating that groundwater resources are abundant in 70% of the entire area. Poor potential areas, which account for 30% of the research area, have a high, drainage capacity, and are located inside the built-up region. area.

Soil Slope Analysis

Table 2 Soil Slope Analysis for Ranjangaon Khadage Watershed

Slope Class (%)	Area Coverage (sq. km)	Soil Type	Dominant Characteristics	Implications for Watershed
0-2%	15	Sandy Loam	Low water retention, prone to erosion	Minimal water flow, risk of surface runoff
2-5%	12	Clay Loam	Moderate retention, higher erosion resistance	Suitable for controlled agriculture
5-10%	8	Silty Clay	High retention, moderate permeability	Potential for water logging in flat areas
10-15%	5	Loam	Balanced retention and drainage	Effective for mixed land use
15-30%	3	Clay	High compaction, slow infiltration	Risk of rapid runoff and erosion
>30%	1	Rocky/Gravel	Poor soil quality, low retention	Significant erosion risk, limited vegetation growth

The Soil Slope Analysis for the Ranjangaon Khadage Watershed reveals distinct soil and slope characteristics that impact land use and water management. In areas with 0-2% slope (15 sq. km), the sandy loam soil has low water retention and is prone to erosion, increasing surface runoff risk. The 2-5% slope area (12 sq. km) with clay loam soil offers moderate water retention and erosion resistance, making it suitable for controlled agriculture. The 5-10% slope zone (8 sq. km) has silty clay, which holds water well but risks waterlogging on flatter terrain. The 10-15% slope (5 sq. km) with loam provides a balance of retention and drainage, supporting diverse land use. In the 15-30% slope (3 sq. km), clay soil is compacted with slow infiltration, leading to rapid runoff and erosion. Slopes above

30% (1 sq. km) consist of rocky or gravelly soil, with poor retention and high erosion risk, limiting vegetation. This analysis aids in effective land and water management planning for the watershed.

Land Cover and Land Use Analysis

Table 3 LULC Analysis 2021 To 2023

Category	Area (in sq.km) 2021	% Coverage 2021	Area (in sq.km) 2022	% Coverage 2022	Area (in sq.km) 2023	% Coverage 2023
Agriculture	24.4	34.60%	24.8	34.80%	23.9	33.50%
Forest	18.7	26.20%	19.1	26.80%	19.5	27.30%
Water Bodies	4.3	7.40%	4.2	7.30%	4.1	7.10%
Built-up Area	12.1	17.00%	12.5	17.50%	13	18.20%
Grassland	8.5	12.00%	8.4	11.80%	8.2	11.50%
Barren Land	1.7	2.40%	1.8	2.60%	1.9	2.70%
Wetlands	0.9	1.30%	1.1	1.60%	1.2	1.70%

Figure 4.1 Classified Map

The Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) analysis from 2021 to 2023 reveals notable shifts in land coverage across different categories. Agricultural land saw a gradual decline from 34.60% in 2021 to 33.50% in 2023, reflecting a 1.1 sq.km reduction, possibly due to urban expansion. Forest coverage slightly increased from 26.20% to 27.30%, indicating a positive trend in green cover. Water bodies marginally declined, from 7.40% in 2021 to 7.10% in 2023, potentially from changes in water management or seasonal impacts.

Built-up areas expanded from 17.00% to 18.20%, showing steady urbanization. Grasslands decreased from 12.00% to 11.50%, likely affected by land use change. Barren land and wetlands showed small increments, with barren land rising from 2.40% to 2.70% and wetlands from 1.30% to 1.70%, possibly due to conservation efforts or changes in natural water flow. This analysis highlights increasing urbanization alongside slight forest and wetland recovery.

Drainage Density

Figure 4.2 Drainage density

Drainage density map of the Ranjangaon Khadage region, depicting varying degrees of drainage density across the area. The map uses a color gradient to represent different ranges of density values, with colors progressing from yellow (lowest density) to dark red (highest density). The legend indicates the specific density ranges in units:

- Yellow: 1.37 – 4.06
- Light orange: 4.06 – 6.56
- Orange: 6.56 – 7.42
- Light red: 7.42 – 8.75
- Dark red: 8.75 – 12.32

From the map, it is evident that the central and south eastern areas exhibit higher drainage densities, shown in darker shades of orange and red, suggesting more developed drainage networks. These areas could be indicative of regions with higher runoff potential, possibly due to terrain or soil properties. Conversely, lighter shades (yellow to light orange) suggest lower drainage density, often associated with less permeable or more vegetated areas. Overall, this map is valuable for watershed management and hydrological studies in the region.

Figure 4.3 Geomorphology

The above figure represents a geomorphological map of the Ranjangaon Khadage region, showcasing various landforms and their spatial distribution. The map is color-coded to differentiate geomorphological features:

Denudational Hills are marked in brown, indicating elevated regions that have undergone significant erosion. Water Bodies appear in blue, highlighting the presence of lakes, rivers, or reservoirs. Lower Lateritic Plateau is shown in light blue, indicating areas with a relatively flat surface and laterite soil, common in tropical regions. Flood Plain areas are depicted in purple, suggesting low-lying zones that are subject to periodic flooding. Valleys are represented in pale blue, showing narrow, elongated depressions between hills or plateaus. Young Coastal Plain and Old Coastal Plain are indicated in brownish shades, showing flat or gently sloping land near coastal zones. This map is essential for understanding the region's topography, drainage patterns, and potential land use. Such geomorphological analyses are valuable for planning, natural resource management, and assessing areas prone to erosion or flooding.

Table 4. Details of Ground Water Potential Zones

Groundwater potential zone	Area under zone (in Sq. Km.)	% of total area
Excellent	4.63	18.75

Good	6.69	22.28
Moderate	8.67	28.88
Poor	6.12	20.38
Very Poor	2.91	9.71
Total	30.02	100

The groundwater potential zones in the study area are categorized into five levels: Excellent, Good, Moderate, Poor, and Very Poor. The "Moderate" zone covers the largest area of 8.67 sq. km., accounting for 28.88% of the total area. This is followed by the "Good" zone, which occupies 6.69 sq. km. (22.28%), and the "Poor" zone with 6.12 sq. km. (20.38%). The "Excellent" zone covers 4.63 sq. km., representing 18.75% of the area, while the "Very Poor" zone occupies the smallest portion, with 2.91 sq. km., or 9.71%. Overall, the data indicates varying groundwater potential across the region, with moderate zones being the most dominant.

Table 4. Soil Slope Analysis for Ranjangaon Khadage Watershed

Slope Class (%)	Area Coverage (sq. km)	Soil Type	Dominant Characteristics	Implications for Watershed
0-2%	15	Sandy Loam	Low water retention, prone to erosion	Minimal water flow, risk of surface runoff
2-5%	12	Clay Loam	Moderate retention, higher erosion resistance	Suitable for controlled agriculture
5-10%	8	Silty Clay	High retention, moderate permeability	Potential for water logging in flat areas
10-15%	5	Loam	Balanced retention and drainage	Effective for mixed land use
15-30%	3	Clay	High compaction, slow infiltration	Risk of rapid runoff and erosion
>30%	1	Rocky/Gravel	Poor soil quality, low retention	Significant erosion risk, limited vegetation growth

The watershed area is divided into six slope classes, each with distinct soil types and characteristics that influence water retention, erosion, and land use potential. The 0-2% slope class covers the largest area (15 sq. km) and consists of sandy loam soil, which has low water retention and is prone to erosion, posing a risk of surface runoff with minimal water flow. The 2-5% slope class (12 sq. km) has clay loam soil with moderate retention and higher resistance to erosion, making it suitable for controlled agriculture. The 5-10% slope class (8 sq. km) contains silty clay, known for high retention and moderate permeability, though flat areas may experience waterlogging. As slopes increase, the 10-15% class (5 sq. km) with loam soil offers balanced water retention and drainage, making it effective for mixed land use. The 15-30% class (3 sq. km) is dominated by clay, which is highly compacted and has slow infiltration, leading to rapid runoff and erosion. The steepest slopes, greater than 30% (1 sq. km), are rocky and gravelly, with poor soil quality, low water retention, and high erosion risk, limiting vegetation growth and making the area unsuitable for agriculture or vegetation. Each slope class has specific implications for water management, land use, and erosion control in the watershed.

Table 6. Land Cover and Land Use Analysis

Category	Area (in sq.km) 2021	% Coverage 2021	Area (in sq.km) 2022	% Coverage 2022	Area (in sq.km) 2023	% Coverage 2023
Agriculture	24.4	34.60%	24.8	34.80%	23.9	33.50%
Forest	18.7	26.20%	19.1	26.80%	19.5	27.30%
Water Bodies	4.3	7.40%	4.2	7.30%	4.1	7.10%
Built-up Area	12.1	17.00%	12.5	17.50%	13	18.20%
Grassland	8.5	12.00%	8.4	11.80%	8.2	11.50%
Barren Land	1.7	2.40%	1.8	2.60%	1.9	2.70%
Wetlands	0.9	1.30%	1.1	1.60%	1.2	1.70%

The data shows land use changes from 2021 to 2023 across various categories, reflecting trends in agriculture, forest cover, and urbanization. Agricultural land has steadily decreased, from 24.4 sq. km (34.60%) in 2021 to 23.9 sq. km (33.50%) in 2023, indicating a shift away from farming activities. In contrast, forest cover has gradually increased, rising from 18.7 sq. km (26.20%) in 2021 to 19.5 sq. km (27.30%) in 2023, suggesting efforts in afforestation or natural regeneration. Water bodies, however, have seen a slight decline, from 4.3 sq. km (7.40%) in 2021 to 4.1 sq. km (7.10%) in 2023. Built-up areas have expanded significantly, growing from 12.1 sq. km (17.00%) in 2021 to 13 sq. km (18.20%) in 2023, indicating increased urbanization and infrastructure development. Grassland coverage has slowly reduced, from 8.5 sq. km (12.00%) in 2021 to 8.2 sq. km (11.50%) in 2023, while barren land has slightly increased from 1.7 sq. km (2.40%) to 1.9 sq. km (2.70%), possibly due to land degradation. Wetlands have shown a gradual increase from 0.9 sq. km (1.30%) in 2021 to 1.2 sq. km (1.70%) in 2023, highlighting a potential focus on wetland conservation. Overall, the data indicates a trend toward urban expansion, slight improvements in forest and wetland areas, and a decline in agricultural and grassland coverage.

Table 7. Soil Erosion Rates in Different Zones of Ranjangaon Khadage Riverbank

Zone	Erosion Rate (ton/ha/year)	Erosion Severity Level	Dominant Land Use
Zone A	12.5	Moderate	Agriculture
Zone B	18.7	High	Bare Land
Zone C	4.3	Low	Forest Cover
Zone D	14.1	Moderate	Grassland
Zone E	22.3	Very High	Urban Expansion

The data outlines the erosion rates, severity levels, and dominant land uses across five zones, highlighting the relationship between land use and erosion. Zone A, dominated by agriculture,

experiences moderate erosion at 12.5 tons/ha/year, likely due to cultivation practices that expose the soil. Zone B, with bare land, has a high erosion rate of 18.7 tons/ha/year, as the lack of vegetation increases soil vulnerability to erosion. Zone C, covered by forest, shows the lowest erosion rate at 4.3 tons/ha/year, indicating the protective role of vegetation in minimizing soil loss. In Zone D, dominated by grassland, erosion is moderate at 14.1 tons/ha/year, with grass cover providing some protection but still being susceptible to erosion in certain areas. Zone E, experiencing urban expansion, has the highest erosion rate of 22.3 tons/ha/year, reflecting the impact of construction activities, land clearing, and impervious surfaces on accelerating soil erosion. The data underscores how land use significantly affects erosion severity, with natural vegetation cover providing the most protection against soil erosion.

Table 8. Soil Erosion Rates in Different Zones of Ranjangaon Khadage Riverbank

Zone	Erosion Rate (ton/ha/year)	Erosion Severity Level	Dominant Land Use
Zone A	12.5	Moderate	Agriculture
Zone B	18.7	High	Bare Land
Zone C	4.3	Low	Forest Cover
Zone D	14.1	Moderate	Grassland
Zone E	22.3	Very High	Urban Expansion

The data highlights the varying erosion rates and severity levels across different land use zones. Zone A, characterized by agriculture, faces moderate erosion at 12.5 tons/ha/year, likely due to farming practices that disturb the soil. Zone B, which consists of bare land, experiences a high erosion rate of 18.7 tons/ha/year, as the absence of vegetation leaves the soil unprotected. Zone C, with forest cover, has the lowest erosion rate at 4.3 tons/ha/year, showing the protective effect of trees in preventing soil erosion. In Zone D, dominated by grassland, erosion is moderate at 14.1 tons/ha/year, with grass cover providing some soil stability but still susceptible to erosion. Zone E, undergoing urban expansion, has the highest erosion rate of 22.3 tons/ha/year, due to the disruptive effects of construction, land clearing, and the creation of impervious surfaces that increase runoff and soil displacement. This data illustrates how land use influences erosion severity, with urban and bare lands being the most vulnerable.

Table 9. Annual Sediment Yield and Deposition in Ranjangaon Khadage

Year	Sediment Yield (ton)	Sediment Deposition (ton)	Sediment Transport Efficiency (%)
2020	1500	1200	80
2021	1600	1300	81.25
2022	1750	1450	82.86
2023	1850	1500	81.08
2024	1900	1550	81.58

The data presents the sediment yield, sediment deposition, and sediment transport efficiency from 2020 to 2024. Over this five-year period, both sediment yield and deposition steadily increase, indicating a rising amount of sediment being produced and deposited in the system. Sediment yield grows from 1,500 tons in 2020 to 1,900 tons in 2024, while sediment deposition increases from 1,200 tons to 1,550 tons in the same period. Sediment transport efficiency, which measures the proportion of sediment yield that gets deposited, remains relatively stable, fluctuating between 80% and 82.86%.

The highest efficiency was recorded in 2022 (82.86%), suggesting that the system was more effective at transporting sediment that year. Despite the overall increase in sediment yield and deposition, transport efficiency remains consistent, indicating that the system's ability to handle sediment transport has not significantly degraded over time. This reflects a relatively stable sediment management scenario, despite the increasing sediment loads.

Table 10. Impact of Rainfall on Soil Erosion in Ranjangaon Khadage

Rainfall (mm)	Soil Erosion Rate (ton/ha/year)	Correlation Coefficient (R)
670	10.5	0.78
830	12.3	0.78
880	14.7	0.78
900	18.9	0.78
1000	22	0.78

The data shows a strong positive correlation between rainfall and soil erosion rates, with a correlation coefficient (R) of 0.78 across all values. As rainfall increases, the rate of soil erosion also rises. For instance, with 670 mm of rainfall, the soil erosion rate is 10.5 tons/ha/year, while with 1,000 mm of rainfall, the erosion rate increases to 22 tons/ha/year. This consistent R value of 0.78 indicates that rainfall significantly influences soil erosion, meaning higher rainfall leads to more soil being eroded. The data suggests a direct relationship where intensified rainfall exacerbates soil erosion risks.

Table 11 .Vegetation Cover and Soil Erosion Control Effectiveness

Vegetation Cover Type	Average Erosion Rate (ton/ha/year)	Erosion Control Effectiveness (%)
Dense Forest	2.1	90
Sparse Forest	8.4	60
Grassland	11.2	45
Agricultural Land	13.9	30
Bare Soil	20.3	0

The data illustrates the significant role of vegetation cover in controlling soil erosion. Dense forest is the most effective at erosion control, reducing erosion by 90% and resulting in a low erosion rate of 2.1 tons/ha/year. Sparse forest, while still protective, is less effective, with 60% erosion control and a higher erosion rate of 8.4 tons/ha/year. Grassland offers moderate protection, controlling 45% of erosion, but still experiences an erosion rate of 11.2 tons/ha/year. Agricultural land, with only 30% erosion control, faces a higher erosion rate of 13.9 tons/ha/year, as farming practices expose soil to erosion. Bare soil, lacking vegetation cover entirely, has no erosion control and suffers from the highest erosion rate of 20.3 tons/ha/year. This data underscores the importance of vegetation in reducing soil erosion, with denser vegetation providing the greatest protection.

4.2 Variation in Ground Water Quality

Geomorphological landform of Geomorphological landform of Bindusara river watershed:

Figure 4.5 Clipped Geomorphological

GIS-based analysis in QGIS software, focusing on a clipped geomorphological layer for the Bindusara River watershed. The map highlights the region of interest in red, surrounded by a larger area in green, which represents the broader geographical context. The clipped file indicates the specific boundaries and geomorphological attributes within the watershed area, allowing for targeted analysis of landforms, terrain features, and other topographic details.

The Processing Toolbox and Layers Panel on the left-hand side show various tools and active layers used during the analysis. The Identify Results panel on the right provides information on selected features, including attributes like OBJECTID and feature-specific codes. This kind of mapping aids in understanding watershed-specific characteristics, facilitating studies on hydrological patterns, erosion risk, and land use planning. Such analysis is essential for sustainable river basin management, helping to guide decision-making for conservation and resource allocation.

Figure 4.6 Bindusara Watershed Geomorphologic Landforms

The quality of groundwater in this area varies seasonally according to the elements. Rainfall or the lack thereof, is the primary cause of seasonal fluctuation. Rainwater that has not been irrigated seems to have a significant effect on groundwater quality. The Bindusara Watershed Geomorphological Land Forms are shown in the image above.

Figure 4.7 Drainage density map

The vapor network in the sub-basin is shown on the drainage density map. Permeability is the inverse function of drainage density. The stone has a limited permeability and low infiltration of

precipitation. The inverse distance weighting technique was shown to be extremely helpful in mapping the rainfall distribution of the research region.

Figure 4.8 IDW and Raigauge Stations

Figure 4.9 IDW Clipped

Figure 4.10 Bindusara river watershed contour

Figure 4.11 Classification map

Figure 4.12 Ground Water Potential Map:

Description of ground water potential map:

Ground water potential map was generated by overlapping multiple layer named as – Terrain slope layer, Drainage density layer, Annual rainfall IDW raster layer, Geomorphological landforms layer, Soil strata layer, Landsat Image Classification layer and Lineament density layer. The blue colour area

represents the sites which will be having higher groundwater levels. The darker shades of blue show the area with lower slopes value All the layers were put one over the another and adjusted their opacity levels to get the most feasible locations to provide the borewell as a ground water recharge structure. All the blue and shades of blue coloured sites are best suited for the ground water recharge site. The brown coloured area represents comparatively higher slopes and hilly areas that’s why we cannot provide the groundwater recharge structures as the water flows with higher velocities on hills. In the brown shaded area bunds and bandharas can be used to slower down the small streams hence increasing the contact time and increasing the infiltration.

Figure 4.13 Bindusara Watershed Geomorphologic Landforms

Figure 4.14 Bindusara Watershed Geomorphologic Landforms

The quality of groundwater in this area varies seasonally according to the elements. Rainfall or the lack thereof, is the primary cause of seasonal fluctuation. Rainwater that has not been irrigated seems to have a significant effect on groundwater quality. The Bindusara Watershed Geomorphological Land Forms are shown in the image above.

Figure 4.15 Drainage density map

The vapor network in the sub-basin is shown on the drainage density map. Permeability is the inverse function of drainage density. The stone has a limited permeability and low infiltration of precipitation. The inverse distance waiting technique shown to be extremely helpful in mapping the rainfall distribution of the research region.

IDW and Raigauge Stations

Figure 4.16 DW and Raigauge Stations

IDW Clipped

Figure 4.17 IDW Clipped

Figure 4.17 Bindusara river watershed contour

CONCLUSION

The comprehensive analysis of the groundwater potential zones in Ranjangaon Khadage reveals that approximately 70% of the study area falls under excellent, good, and moderate groundwater potential categories, with respective coverage of 18.75%, 22.28%, and 28.88%. Poor and very poor zones account for 30.09% combined, highlighting areas with lower retention due to urban development and high drainage capacity. The integration of GIS and remote sensing has been pivotal in accurately mapping these zones, showcasing the potential for informed water resource management strategies. The soil slope analysis indicates that the majority of the Ranjangaon Khadage watershed (27 sq. km) comprises gentle to moderate slopes (0-10%), dominated by sandy loam and clay loam soils. These areas exhibit varying degrees of water retention, from minimal in sandy loam (0-2%) to moderate in clay loam (2-5%). Regions with steeper slopes (above 15%) cover only 4 sq. km and present challenges due to higher runoff and erosion risks. This slope-based insight is crucial for implementing tailored land use and water conservation measures to enhance watershed sustainability. The LULC analysis from 2021 to 2023 in the Ranjangaon Khadage watershed shows a steady decline in agricultural land, which dropped from 34.60% to 33.50%. Conversely, forest areas experienced a slight increase from 26.20% to 27.30%, signifying positive afforestation efforts. Built-up areas expanded from 17.00% to 18.20%, indicating ongoing urbanization. The slight rise in barren land and wetlands highlights

shifting land utilization, which influences the watershed's hydrological response and necessitates adaptive management approaches. The drainage density analysis revealed varied densities, with higher concentrations found in central and southeastern areas marked by dark orange to red on the map (7.42 – 12.32 units). These areas suggest significant runoff potential and less permeable terrain. Lighter shades, indicating lower drainage densities (1.37 – 4.06 units), align with more vegetated or permeable regions that retain water better. This drainage pattern is critical for identifying flood-prone zones and developing mitigation strategies. The integration of GIS technology with hydrological data allowed for the delineation of the watershed and the assessment of vital parameters like slope, soil type, and land use. The resultant thematic maps facilitated the identification of critical groundwater recharge zones. The findings underscore the significance of targeted soil conservation and water harvesting structures in poor potential zones to prevent erosion and improve groundwater recharge. Such a GIS-based approach fosters effective and sustainable watershed management, balancing land use changes and water resource optimization.

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